

Securing Cloud Environment Using Hybrid (Adaptive Public Key) Model

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Abstract:

Although data security has always been important, it is now even more so given the significance of cloud computing and the enormous amounts of complex data it holds. In cloud computing, having data accessible at all times is vital, as is collecting and preserving data without loss or corruption. The use of appropriate algorithms is one of the most important aspects of security. These protocols protect data by limiting unauthorized access. In order to ensure the security of your data, you need to conduct research on the security risks associated with public clouds. The purpose of this document is to provide an in-depth review of public clouds and the

security issues associated with them. In order to review the literature review that provides an in-depth understanding of cloud storage and security issues, it is necessary to overcome several obstacles. As a result, based on an analysis of cloud architecture, we provide the data security model that can be applied to cloud computing. Our cloud computing data security model is now better. Lastly, the work can be done in a direction that benefits from faster encryption times and increased data secrecy by utilising machine learning and authentication technologies for safe cloud storage.

Keywords: *Cloud Computing, Hybrid Model, Security, storage, Advanced Encryption Standard and cryptographic algorithms.*

Introduction

Data is a discrete piece of knowledge. It is essential for the creation of information. Text, images, audio, and video all qualify as data. Keeping track of and storing this data is crucial.

Data is now primarily kept in the cloud. On the cloud, data can be stored in a variety of ways. The security of cloud-stored data, however, is increasingly crucial.

Cloud computing is a paradigm for widely available, useful, on-demand network access to a pool of reconfigurable computing resources (such as networks, servers, storage, apps, and services) that can be swiftly provisioned and released with little management effort or service provider interaction.

The storage of data is one of the many resources that clients can access through the vital and efficient service of cloud computing. More vulnerabilities exist for sensitive data. In the context of cloud computing, sensitive data entails information from numerous fields and specialties. Sensitive information needs to be kept private and secure. The most important and significant factor is therefore data security (Binita & Blessy, 2020).

The majority of this data originates from or is stored in the cloud, a new computing paradigm that is reshaping many ecosystems by giving businesses access to computer resources with simple deployment, connectivity, setup, automation, and scalability. According to Chunqiang et al. (2017), employing the cloud is an effective method of outsourcing data to a server that can store vast amounts of data and swiftly respond to user access requests. Furthermore, Samir et al. (2017) found that cloud computing looks to be the best platform for hosting huge data workloads. Additionally, according to Stergiou and Psannis (2017), cloud computing aims to offer access to information and data without the restrictions given by the need for physical equipment.

Keeping sensitive data out of the wrong hands is crucial for the survival of many organizations. Since there may be grave consequences if these sensitive data ended up in the wrong hands. The reputation of many businesses or organizations will be in jeopardy, for example, if private information like trade secrets, project documents, and customer profiles are leaked to their competitors (Alneyadi et al., 2016).

In light of this, storing data in a cloud environment presents a number of security challenges, including confidentiality, availability, and integrity (Bentajer et al., 2018). The cloud presents increasingly difficult security

challenges. All information can be viewed publicly, therefore many users run the risk of storing and retrieving information publicly. Data protection is necessary because so many firms are migrating their data to the cloud. Numerous studies have been conducted so far with security in cloud computing in mind. As security is the top issue for users, various authors have offered various approaches to achieve security.

This paper's primary goal is to expand our understanding of employing a hybrid model to detect and stop unauthorized access in a cloud setting. Using on-site cloud data centers, this solution will safely store the sensitive content.

Challenges for Implementing Cloud Computing

In the last several years, cloud computing has grown dramatically. Using pools of frequently virtualized resources, cloud computing is a novel approach to providing IT services. It typically provides self-service, elastic, and dynamically scalable access over a network. However, this novel approach faces several challenges from multiple directions, such as:

1. Security: Cloud computing security is the key issue with cloud services investments. The reason is that a third-party service is handling and storing your data without your knowledge. concerning once a day or so, news reports surface concerning problems involving a certain company, like failed authentication, credentials being stolen, account hacking, data breaches, and other issues. This further increases the user's skepticism. Cloud Service Providers have begun to increase security. You can take caution by making sure the service provider has established access control guidelines and a safe user identity management system. In addition, confirm that it complies with database security and privacy laws.

2. Loss or leakage of data: Permanent data loss is worrisome for both individuals and businesses. Data saved in the cloud may be lost for reasons other than hostile attackers, as is clear. A physical disaster or an unfavorable removal by the cloud service provider could

result in the permanent exposure of client data (Ramachandra, 2017).

3. Password security: When more people use a single cloud account, the security of the password becomes increasingly compromised. Anyone who discovers a user's password or gains access to the cloud will be able to access sensitive information that belongs to that individual. The business should use multiple levels of authentication in this case and make sure that credentials are kept private. Passwords should also be changed often, especially when an employee leaves a company. When allowing others access to user names and passwords, users should proceed with caution.

4. Interoperability and portability: This is a problem with cloud computing because applications need to be portable and able to move between cloud providers without being tied in for a long period of time. The flexibility of switching from one cloud provider to another is constrained by the sophistication required. New problems, like tracking data flow and constructing a secure network from the bottom up, are brought on by evolving cloud innovations. Another difficulty is that consumers cannot access it from everywhere. However, the cloud service provider can fix this so that consumers can safely access the cloud from anywhere (Ramachandran, 2017).

5. Hybrid cloud complexity: A hybrid cloud environment for any business is typically a disorganised jumble of different cloud application development and service providers, along with private and public clouds that are all running simultaneously. Standardised user interfaces, consistent data, and business-oriented analytics are lacking in these intricate cloud ecosystems. In a hybrid cloud environment, cloud computing issues related to scalability, integration, and disaster recovery are magnified.

6. Reliability and high availability: Two of the most important problems facing cloud computing are dependability and high availability (HA). Whereas availability refers to the chance that a system will be up and operating at any given time, reliability is the possibility that it will be. Due to the fact that most businesses depend

on outside services, cloud solutions need to be robust and trustworthy. There are frequent interruptions because cloud services are still not always available. Using internal or external solutions, it is imperative to monitor the services being rendered (Ramachandra, 2017).

Review of Related works

The term Cloud is used because it reflects the dynamic scalability, abstract boundaries, and ambiguous location, similar to a natural cloud. The cloud is not a collection of physical hardware, software, or services. It involves the amalgamation and incorporation of extensive information technologies.

The information technology sector can now use computer resources more effectively and efficiently thanks to a technology called cloud computing. A flexible and powerful paradigm, cloud computing is changing many facets of the IT sector (Isaac et al. 2018). It is an amalgamation of distributed, parallel, and multitenant computing models that utilise various technologies such as virtualization, grid computing, utility computing, and autonomic computing (Kaur et al. 2017). According to Kumar et al. (2017), cloud computing provides technology services that are adaptable, instantaneously available, and robust.

The majority of users now rely on a wide range of computing services, with cloud computing serving as their foundation. Without having to own or manage physical computer resources, Han et al. (2018) allows users to access and distribute computing resources via the Internet (Oredo et al., 2019). Cloud computing prioritises service delivery over the delivery of technology (Mohsen & Jeremy, 2019) and also enables global access to files, documents, and videos from any location.

The data stored in the cloud is highly sensitive; this therefore makes the cloud vulnerable and target of most intruders; the cloud therefore requires robust security measures. The viability of numerous organizations hinges on the prevention of unauthorized access to this data. Due to the potential for severe repercussions, it

is crucial to prevent unauthorized access of this sensitive data. For example, the reputation of numerous businesses or organizations may be undermined when confidential information such as proprietary information, project files, and customer profiles are disclosed to their rivals (Alneyadi et al. 2016).

Bo (2015) pointed that a major challenge in creating a secure cloud system is preventing unauthorised access to sensitive data. This challenge is heavily dependent on the selection of authentication and encryption algorithms, which are responsible for ensuring authenticity and confidentiality, respectively. This work explores different facets of authentication and encryption algorithms for enhancing the security of cloud systems. It delves into authenticated encryption modes of operation, block cyphers, password hashing algorithms, and password-less/two-factor authentication mechanisms.

The author of this paper introduces two innovative password hashing algorithms, Pleco and Plectron, which are built upon established cryptographic structures and primitives. The distinguishing feature of the Pleco and Plectron designs lies in their integration of both symmetric-key and asymmetric-key algorithms.

Pan (2019) study provides evidence that the privacy and security concerns are major factors influencing the popularity of cloud computing services. Attribute-based encryption (ABE), trust, reputation, access control, and other techniques have been the focus of many research projects recently aimed at protecting cloud computing privacy. Nevertheless, these initiatives are dispersed and lack a unified structure.

This paper reviews and analyses relevant research achievements in a thorough and systematic manner. In addition to offering a framework for privacy protection, the text attempts to address the architecture, ideas, and constraints of cloud computing. In addition, a number of encryption techniques are covered and analysed, including ABE, KP-ABE, CP-ABE, access structure, revocation mechanism, multi-authority, fine-grained, trace mechanism, PRE, hierarchical encryption, SE, trust,

reputation, and the extension of traditional access control.

In their 2016 survey paper, Shyam & Amit (2016), present a comprehensive analysis of the cloud security issue. This paper examines various existing methodologies pertaining to data encryption and message authentication. Upon examining the current methodologies, we have identified the problems and difficulties that arise when processing data in the cloud. This paper proposes the use of attribute-based encryption and attribute-based authentication simultaneously, rather than relying solely on encryption or authentication, to enhance security during communication over the cloud.

This paper identifies the challenges related to ensuring secure communication over cloud networks and it examines the reasons for requiring encryption, message signing, and verification in order to ensure confidentiality, data integrity, and message authentication when providing services over the cloud. Maximum security measures can be attained by implementing both encryption and authentication during the processing of data on the cloud.

The literature review reveals the existence of various Cloud Security techniques or methods pertaining to detective approaches. Nevertheless, there is still a significant amount of work that needs to be accomplished in order to automate the suggested approach. This involves developing a system that can effectively input data into the relevant data mining tool, as well as utilising Adaptive Public Key Algorithm in conjunction with Big Data technologies.

Therefore, it is necessary to employ the Adaptive Public Key Algorithm to safeguard the cloud and proactively prevent the occurrence of Big Data breaches, particularly in relation to semi-structured textual data. The implementation of this design will mitigate the potential for information leakage and guarantee the integrity and confidentiality of the data. Additionally, any unauthorised modifications to the data will be readily identified.

Hybrid Cloud

Hybrid cloud refers to a unified cloud service that combines the use of private and public clouds to carry out specific tasks within an organisation. It is the amalgamation of two or more cloud service deployment models, namely Private, Public, and Community. Users can enhance the capacity or capability of their system by combining, integrating, or customising it with another cloud package or service.

In a hybrid cloud, resources are managed and provided either internally or by external providers. The project encompassed multiple services and networks, raising significant concerns regarding security issues (Dave et al. 2018). Izang et al. (2017) demonstrated that a hybrid cloud integrates multiple cloud deployment models. An organisation utilises a combination of private cloud and third-party public cloud services to host their resources, with careful consideration given to planning between the two platforms.

A hybrid security model, as defined by Rahul & Himanshu (2016), is one that employs a single model made up of numerous security features that cover more than one security area and can simultaneously work on all the various security-related issues. Additionally, it guarantees the highest level of security and makes data flow within businesses fully safe, preventing any intrusion and loss to outside parties.

Businesses can utilize a hybrid cloud to operate non-essential apps on the public cloud while keeping sensitive data and critical applications on-premises in a private cloud. Services offered by integrating cloud components are developing, barriers are being removed, and enablers are being created. Trusting that an organization's data is secure and private is a fundamental worry; achieving this trust is a significant step in the adoption of cloud computing in its entirety.

This paper presents a thorough and systematic review and analysis of pertinent research achievements. The text aims to address cloud computing's architecture, concepts, and limitations in addition to providing a framework for privacy protection. In addition, a number of

encryption techniques are covered and analysed, including ABE, KP-ABE, CP-ABE, access structure, revocation mechanism, multi-authority, fine-grained, trace mechanism, PRE, hierarchical encryption, SE, trust, reputation, and the extension of traditional access control.

A new hybrid algorithm combining the Homographic and Blowfish algorithms was proposed by Sajay et al. (2018). Using a homomorphic technique, the input text was first encrypted in this. After that, the Blowfish technique is used to encrypt the output. The output that is obtained is the final encryption text. The investigation comes to the conclusion that the novel algorithm is superior than established algorithms.

There is still much work to be done, though, to automate the suggested approach so that data may be fed into the proper data mining tool, and by extension employing Adaptive Public Key Algorithm which is a Hybrid Cloud Model.

The term adaptive security refers to a security solution that continuously learns and adjusts to the changing environment in response to evolving risks and foresees hazards before they materialize. Adaptive, autonomous, and evolving security involves gathering contextual data from the system and its surroundings, analyzing that data, and coming to decisions through learning. It also involves responding to changes with the forms and methods of adaptation listed above and modifying or creating new functions and structures.

The Adaptive Public Key Algorithm must be used to protect the cloud and aid in preventing data leakage before it happens, with a focus on semi-structured data (text data). The end result of this design will reduce the likelihood of information leakage, safeguard the confidentiality and security of the data, and make any data update obvious.

Depending on the needs of the company, the aforementioned procedure can be modified to match a variety of characteristic criteria. It seeks to provide a more reliable and complex access control approach given the main use cases they serve. Additionally, it aims to complete the

amalgamation process quicker than with traditional methods.

Methodology

Descriptive research methodology is used in this study. This method was chosen because it employed the random sampling technique, which entails gathering data (including information about Cloud Computing and Data with regard to University systems) from sources of documented information, such as documentaries, scientific research, browsed materials, and written articles. Google Scholar was also used to broaden the scope of the study, analyse the data, evaluate the findings, and display the information acquired.

The widely used methods of Object-Oriented Design Methodology (OOADM) and Structured Systems Analysis and Design Methodology (SSADM) are also available. By outlining the detected problems in a methodical manner, SSADM / OOADM offers a development roadmap for systems.

SSADM/OOADM contains the following:

1. Structured standards, which describe the organizational structure of a development project utilizing explicitly stated activities, interfaces between them, and tangible deliverables with precise definitions.
2. Technical manuals provide clear guidance on when and how to use the right techniques, protocols, and standards throughout the system development process.
3. Documentation standards, which give developers a mechanism to meticulously record the outcomes of their work. This approach looks at the requirements for the issue, creates a solution, and then uses a programming language or database to implement the solution.

Proposed Work

Adaptive Public Key Algorithm, a hybrid cloud management model, will provide data management across cloud servers and the

framework for private and public cloud services to run their client applications and examine security trends. any company using the hybrid cloud system to manage client-level data, manage all services, and provide generic service products. Understanding how programmes, software, legacy systems, and storage components are managed within the established security constraints is crucial.

The hybrid cloud system will ascertain how frequently clients utilize the services and what security access procedures are implemented by the service provider at the client location. The administration of secured information access will include an interface with APIs that can be used to navigate user apps and assess performance.

The system framework for the suggested model is depicted in the diagram below, which will make it easier to integrate all of the security-based functionalities in the environment for accessing cloud services. As shown in the following diagram (Figure 1).

Security-related operations at the client end system are shown in the above diagram (figure 1). In the hybrid cloud model, the operational functional and process-based operations for the multiple information management access platforms are built and assessed. To assure the security level and service dependability feature, many control processes and segments will be followed in the service access environment.

A novel paradigm incorporating hashing, one-time-password (OTP) validation, and hybrid cryptography is presented in this work. It was developed using HTML, PHP, and MySQL. ElGamal and the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) algorithms are the two primary encryption methods employed in it. Furthermore, the SHA-256 hash function is employed to verify data integrity and minimise the likelihood that confidential data could be compromised by an external party, like a cloud service provider. Each approach was selected after a thorough comparison study, with many considerations taken into consideration.

Figure 1. Hybrid Cloud Management System Architecture

Source: Ramamoorthy & Poorvadevi, 2018

A symmetric cryptographic method known as AES or Rijndael uses a substitution-permutation network to encrypt data in a block. In a formal call by NIST in 1999, Rijndael was one of the shortlisted algorithms. Following an analysis of many AES criteria, the NIST decided to use it in place of the Data Encryption Standard (DES) to protect sensitive information. As a result, AES was widely used in hardware and software by many businesses, including governments, to encrypt highly sensitive data in recent years.

However, three block cyphers with different key sizes are included in AES. Every block cypher has the ability to encrypt and decrypt data in 128-bit blocks using cryptographic keys that are 128-, 192-, or 256-bit in size. Depending on the various key sizes chosen, a different round of operation on that particular cypher will be employed. As an example, AES-128 has ten rounds, AES-192 has twelve, and AES-192 has fourteen. A round consists of multiple steps, such as adding the round key, mixing columns, permuting, and replacing bytes. Using the same encryption key, reverse rounds are employed during decryption to change ciphertext back into plaintext.

Implementation

The concept that data is the primary asset of businesses and the government has gained widespread acceptance due to the quick growth of information technology. The best priority now is figuring out how to secure digital assets. Additionally, PHP 7.2.1, MySQL, Apache, TWOFISH, and the Hybrid method were used to implement this study project. The tests are conducted using an Intel Core TM i5 processor clocked at 2.30 GHz, 8 GB of RAM, and Windows 10 64-bit. The experimental environment uses PHP's default settings.

PHP (Hypertext Preprocessor) is the server-side programming language utilised in this web development. PHP is often used as a general-purpose scripting language for building dynamic and interactive web pages. It performs the role of a server-side language that can be combined with HTML to facilitate the addition of features to a website without the need for outside files. Additionally, a PHP extension that binds OpenSSL library functions for decryption, symmetric and asymmetric encryption, and other cryptographic operations is offered.

The data is encrypted and may only be read and downloaded by the authorised user, which eliminates privacy issues, allowing any authorised user to safely save their data or file in cloud storage. Before being transferred to the cloud, the original data is encrypted using AES to turn it into an unintelligible format and add the necessary secret key information. It is also necessary to encrypt the matching secret key using the owner's ElGamal public key, which is generated during registration.

To access the original contents of the file, the user must select it from the list and input their own private key. Subsequently, an automated decryption procedure will be executed to retrieve the initial data and assess its hash value against the hash value produced and stored in the database throughout the upload procedure. Only after the file has been successfully decrypted and verified will the SHA-2 algorithm allow the file to be downloaded. In order to ensure that the data wasn't altered or corrupted during transmission, this is done.

The information kept in the cloud may also be highly private and sensitive for people. In order to prevent any unauthorized access from outside parties, the 2FA mechanism is also used in this proposed strategy. Users must always enter a six-digit OTP to sign in, which is valid for three minutes after the system has confirmed they are who they say they are.

Result and Discussion

Utilizing an adaptive public key technique, the study was conducted to identify and track unauthorized access. Three data engines—the customer database, university database, and unauthorized access database each with distinct roles in the fraud detection and monitoring system—were also used in the study, which was carried out using two modules, Admin and User, and their respective submodules.

The staff customer database and the unauthorized access database Detection System (FDS) are cross-checked. The personal identification number (PIN) will also be requested, and its validity will be checked by

database comparison. Confirmation codes, email addresses, phone numbers, and security questions were all generated using the public key.

The algorithm uses a prediction algorithm on these data patterns to determine if a specific activity is fake or legitimate. If the pattern differs from the past action, the system concludes that it is unauthorized user access and it generates an alert message to the valid user and admin as well as the fraudster details and location through internet protocol (IP) address that will be automatically sent and stored in the unauthorized access database. If the pattern does not differ from the past action, the system concludes that it is not unauthorized user access.

The knowledge gained from this study has greatly contributed to our understanding of the prevalence of the fraudulent acts that intrusions started as a result of the several reasons that were discussed. The study's knowledge-advancing findings were as follows:

1. Using an adaptive public key technique, create a unauthorized access detection model driven by data experts. Instead of employing the two-stage model often employed in fraud detection algorithms, a hybrid approach is used to create the unauthorized access detection system. This strategy makes use of both public key and neural network algorithms to achieve a synergy that better handles the university unauthorized access database problem.
2. The study strengthened the reliability and effectiveness of the public key and neural network model as a research tool and established a firm foundation for sophisticated detection techniques to be applied in a working unauthorized access detection system.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The main goal of any cloud data storage strategy is to make data accessible easily while maintaining data security. Security must be considered in any cloud data storage solution to guarantee effectiveness and safety. We propose a secure approach to cloud-based data security in this paper. The method provides a solution to a

number of cloud security issues, such as protecting data from theft and guarding against a fake authorized user who compromises cloud security.

This study examines numerous issues and challenges with cloud computing that jeopardize data security and privacy. Our solution provides the benefits and effectiveness of cloud computing security, including better cloud data encryption. Users of cloud computing can benefit from its security and scalability of data communication. The security requirements for cloud computing, such as encryption, authorization, identity, and authentication, are met by our design.

We suggest putting this strategy into practice because it will aid organizations in identifying, monitoring, and reducing unauthorized access. Customers and non-customers alike would be encouraged to use the e-system unauthorized access detection system as a result. However, additional research is needed to fully understand the features of huge data sets and the associated sophisticated processing technique, as well as the reliability of client-server connection. To make the model more applicable to a larger range of application scenarios, future research may concentrate on fusing the public key technique with other well-known security mechanisms.

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